

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF WIDELY USED TERMS IN THE BANKING FIELD IN UZBEK-ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT. This article provides information about the appearance of the terms used in the banking sector and their characteristics, their importance are compared using the example of the Uzbek and English languages. The history of terminology, the role of the terms used in the development of the banking industry, the methods and tools of the terms that entered the Uzbek language were also given. Moreover, a number of terms used in the banking industry today are comparatively analyzed.

Key words: terms, terminology, methods, banking sector, banking industry, tools.

Today, the development of science and technology is developing rapidly. Various new terms, new views and new ideas have entered science, which encourages people to live in sync with the times. As an example, we can cite the activity of the banking sector. It is inappropriate to call this field a very new field. The reason is that in ancient times there were organizations that performed banking operations, but they could not fulfill the task of today's banks. The basis for the emergence and activity of banks is the need for money exchange. In this case, Europe can be shown as a bright example. In the Middle Ages, there was no single system of (monetary) coins. Trade was conducted through the coins of different countries, cities, and even individuals. All coins have different weights, shapes and denominations. Therefore, specialists who deal with coins and can carry out exchanges are located with their exchange tables in places where there is an intense trade. Therefore, the word "bank" comes from the Italian word "banco" which means the table in front of the money changer. Similar operations were carried out not only in Rome, but also in other European countries such as Greece, as well as in a number of Eastern countries (Abdullayeva, 2017, 14b). Today, the role of banks in the world economy and politics is very significant. For this reason, the study of special terms used in this field is one of the urgent issues facing linguists.

First of all, if we define the concept of the term, it can be interpreted in different ways. The terms are defined differently in different literatures. For example, for logicians, a term is a word that refers to a set of descriptions (or descriptions) of a specific object and is applied to it. Any word in any language can be a term (Dadaboyev, 2019, 4-5b). It can be seen that in order to give the quality of a term to a certain word, the word must be widely used in a field. Any word can be a term. But no person can classify all the terms in the world. Because of this, the terms are used only within a certain field. For example, terms used by linguists are completely unfamiliar to pharmacists, or vice versa. But we can say that the use of terms is not geographically specific. That is, they are used anywhere in the world in their field. The terminology of the banking system is based on economics. Neologisms play an important role in the emergence of terms. When any term enters the Uzbek language, it is necessary to pay attention to its following aspects: the compatibility of the term with the sound system of the Uzbek language; whether it has an Uzbek alternative; to the necessity of copying or

translation; to the meaning of the economic term; to its simplicity and fluency; to its essence and correctness.

Banking terms entered the Uzbek language mainly in two ways. The first is by finding an alternative version of the term in a foreign language in Uzbek.

For example, we can see client-client, auction-auction, percentage-percentage.

Secondly, we can observe how a word from a foreign language enters the Uzbek language through the method of transliteration or transcription. As an example, we can cite account-account, shareholder-shareholder, credit-credit.

The terms mentioned above are considered to be the terms that entered the Uzbek language through the Russian language.

Below we will quote some of the terms that are widely used in the banking sector today, comparing them with the English language.

Account. A type of financial property or financial obligation that is held and owned under your name. When you open a financial account — whether it's a checking account, savings account, CD or money market account—you have certain rights and responsibilities as an account holder.

An invoice is an invoice confirming the delivery of goods and services provided by the seller in the name of the buyer and their full value. The invoice contains information about the terms of the sales transaction, including volume, price, value, sales and delivery methods.

APR (Annual Percentage Rate). The total annualized cost of a loan. When you borrow money, whether it's via a credit card, car loan or another loan, the lender is required to disclose the APR, so you understand the full cost of borrowing the money.

The annual interest rate is a certain percentage of the amount of the loan (deposit) that the borrower (bank) pays for one year to use the loan (deposit).

ATM (Automated Teller Machine). A convenient location for basic banking transactions, such as withdrawing cash, depositing checks or making balance inquiries. Many banks offer access to a network of fee-free ATMs.

Automated money transfer machine/ATM is a software-technical complex designed to automatically issue and receive funds, as well as make payments for goods and services through an ATM, prepare documents confirming relevant operations there is a possibility.

Check. A type of financial instrument that instructs the check writer's bank to make a payment to the recipient indicated on the check. Some people write paper checks and other people use their bank's online bill pay feature to issue electronically generated checks.

Check . A written order of the bank account holder to a bank or credit institution to pay a certain amount of money to a person; a monetary document, a type of security.

Credit. Credit generally refers to your ability to borrow—the willingness of banks and other lenders to extend a loan to you.

Credit . Debt/loan in the form of goods or money subject to repayment (together with interest payments); determines the economic relationship between the debtor and the creditor.

Electronic signatures. Under US federal law, electronic signatures or esignatures have the same legal validity as signatures on paper contracts. Online contracts may have the same legal status as paper contracts.

Electronic signature. A digital signature on an electronic document that enables identification of the owner.

Investments. Investments are financial assets that are purchased and sold by investors, with the goal of earning a return on investment (ROI). Common types of investments include stocks, bonds, mutual funds, index funds, exchange traded funds and real estate. There are also various alternative investments like gold, commodities, fine art, wine and more. Unlike bank savings and checking accounts, investments are not FDIC insured and have a risk of loss.

Investments. Material and intangible assets and rights to them, including rights to intellectual property objects, as well as reinvestments, which are invested by the investor in the social sphere, entrepreneurship, scientific and other types of activities on the basis of risks for the purpose of profit, they include funds (money in national and foreign currency), including targeted bank deposits, shares, stocks, bonds, promissory notes and other securities; movable and immovable property (buildings, structures, equipment, machines and other material assets); intellectual property rights, including formalized, patented or unpatented (know-how) technical, technological, commercial and technical documents, skills and production experience necessary for the organization of this or that type of production may include other knowledge, as well as other values not prohibited by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan .

Online banking. Online banks , also called digital or internet banks, operate primarily via the internet. You can manage your accounts at an online bank from a computer or mobile device from anywhere at any time.

Online banking. (also called internet banking) is a web-based method of banking that allows a bank's customers to complete their banking transactions and related activities on the respective bank's website. By registering as an online shopper with your bank (or a new bank), you can access online almost all the common services that your bank provides at local branches.

In conclusion, we can say that banking terms widely used in English are also used in Uzbek. There is no boundary between them in terms of meaning and application.

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